

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17168758

Construction And Infrastructure Development In Nigeria: Opportunities And Challenges

Lead Author:

Prof. Okeke Gerald Ndubuisi
(Professor of Climate Change & Environmental Sustainability)
FNisafetyE, FISPON, etc.
Highstone Global University, Texas, USA.

2nd Author:

Associate Professor Cynthia Amaka OBIORAH PhD
Centre for Occupational Health Safety and Environment,
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
cynthia.obiora@cohseuniport.edu.ng
Engr. Prof. Theophilus Aku Ugah
Engineer/Environmentalist/Oil & Gas Professional
Highstone Global University, Texas, USA.
theogah2004@gmail.com.

Engr. Prof. Sony Emeka Ali
(Professor of Civil Engineering & Project Management).
FNSE, FNICE, FNisafetyE, FNIStructE.
Highstone Global University, Texas, USA.

Prof. Ogechukwu Ukandu
Highstone Global University, Texas, USA.
Email: ogelic@yahoo.com

Prof Engr. Harriet Chimezie
Ph.D. FAcn, MAEIAN, MIAENG, MNSE, MIAIA
Professor of Climate Change and Environmental Sustainability
Highstone Global University, Texas, USA.

Engr. Dr. Cletus Onyemhese Agbakhamen
Email ID: cletus.agbakhamen@chevron.com; ceestrides@gmail.com
Phone number: +2348039760095

Dr. Omatseyione Nesiama
Health Safety & Environmentalist/Geologist/Oil & Gas Professional
Email: otsevione@gmail.com.

Engr. Dr. Pupu Ogheneteme Okoro (Ph.D.)
Project Management, Highstone Global University, Texas, USA.

Engr. Mbanaso Maryann Ijeoma (Mrs.)
Email: chineyechidera@gmail.com
Phone Number: +2348037874537

ABSTRACT

Nigerian Infrastructure rating is currently at level F⁻ and on a grade point average of 1.8/5.0 which is a percentage score of 36 over 100. Other parameters of development such as Human Development Index, Sustainable Development Goals, Vulnerability Index and Global Competitiveness placed Nigeria on 0.548, 54.58%, 0.462 and 48.33% respectively. Massive investment in infrastructure development through the Public Private Partnership Scheme is the lowest hanging fruit in terms of funding for government even as revenue resources get leaner with time. The authors relied on extensive secondary sources backed with infrastructure development experiences of over three decades to arrive at their conclusion and recommendations. \$150 billion infrastructure investment gap for 30 years is a mix of challenges and opportunities to warrant innovative solutions towards closing the deficit.

Keywords: sustainable development goals, human development index, global competitiveness index, vulnerability index, infrastructure deficit, infrastructure development.

INTRODUCTION

Just like many developmental issues, construction and infrastructure development in Nigeria is a mix bag of opportunities and challenges. At the centre of progress of any country is the possession of functional infrastructural facilities; Umar, Ogbu and Ereke (2019). World over, infrastructure development trigger economic growth and development. Infrastructural deficit common in most developing countries including Nigeria frustrates the creation of reliable path to national development. This is occasioned by the near impossibility of flow of foreign direct investment and advancement of critical and non-critical sectors of the economy.

The word infrastructure is a combination of the Latin prefix “infra”, meaning “below” and “structure”. Hornby (2000) defines infrastructure as the basic systems and services that are necessary for a country or an organization, for example buildings, transport, water and power supplies and administrative systems. Infrastructure can be defined as the basic physical and organizational structures needed for the operation of a society or enterprise, or the services and facilities necessary for an economy to function. The term can also refer to the technical structures that support a society, such as roads, water supply, sewers, power grids, telecommunications, and so forth (Kumar, 2005).

Infrastructure refers to the basic physical and organizational structures required for proper operation of a society including roads, buildings, bridges, health services. It is “the set of interconnected structural elements that provides framework for supporting an entire structure of development.” Oyedele (2012). The absence of these facilities and services makes development very difficult.

A solid infrastructure base is imperative for economic growth as it promotes productivity while facilitating more effective service delivery. Economic stability and long-term development are occasioned by investments in key sectors such as water, electricity and transportation; Audu and Adeiza (2024).

A US National Research Council Panel (1987), in an attempt to clarify the term called it “public works infrastructure”, referring to: “.....both specific functional modes - highways, streets, roads, and bridges, mass transit, airports and airways, water supply and water resources, wastewater management, solid-waste treatment and disposal, electric power generation and transmission, telecommunications and hazardous waste management – and the combined system these modal elements comprise. A comprehension of infrastructure spans not only these public works facilities, but also the operating procedures, management practices, and development policies that interact together with societal demands and the physical world to facilitate the transport of people and goods, provision of water for drinking and

a variety of other uses, safe disposal of society's waste products, provision of energy where it is needed, and transmission of information within and between communities.”

Unless otherwise stated, the term infrastructure will be used in this study in the sense of technical structures or physical networks that support society; Ali (2012).

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's infrastructure development faces significant challenges, hindering economic growth, sustainability, and human development, with the country's infrastructure stock estimated at only 30% of GDP, far below the 70% international benchmark set by the World Bank. The nation requires substantial investment in various types of engineering infrastructure, including transportation, energy and power, water and sanitation, and urban infrastructure, all of which are crucial for enhancing connectivity, facilitating trade, increasing electricity generation, ensuring access to clean water and sanitation, and supporting sustainable urban development. Sustainable development is critical, requiring careful consideration of environmental, social, and economic impacts, and civil engineers must design and construct infrastructure projects that minimize environmental degradation, promote social equity, and support economic growth.

However, civil engineers face challenges such as inadequate funding, poor maintenance culture, corruption, and a lack of skilled manpower, all of which affect the quality and sustainability of infrastructure projects. Infrastructure development is essential for Nigeria's economic growth, as it enhances productivity, attracts investments, and creates employment opportunities, but the country's human development index (HDI) ranking is impacted by infrastructure challenges, and its vulnerability to climate change and natural disasters underscores the importance of designing resilient and adaptable infrastructure. While infrastructure development presents opportunities for public-private partnerships, adoption of smart technologies, and sustainable and green infrastructure, it also poses challenges such as inadequate funding, corruption, and sustainability and environmental concerns, highlighting the need for effective project management and balancing infrastructure development with environmental and social considerations.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study examined the construction and infrastructure development in Nigeria; exploring the opportunities and challenges. Specifically, the answered the following objectives:

1. Examine the current state and types of engineering infrastructure in Nigeria.
2. Investigate the role of sustainable development in Nigeria's infrastructure development.
3. Explore the role of civil engineers in Nigeria's infrastructure development.
4. Analyze the impact of infrastructure development on Nigeria's economic growth.
5. Assess Nigeria's global ranking in terms of human development index (HDI) and its implications for infrastructure development.
6. Identify opportunities and challenges in Nigeria's infrastructure development.
7. Evaluate how infrastructures improve quality of life in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study addressed the following research questions:

1. What is the current state and types of engineering infrastructure in Nigeria, and how does it impact the country's economic growth and development?
2. How can sustainable development be integrated into Nigeria's infrastructure development?
3. What is the role of civil engineers in Nigeria's infrastructure development?
4. What is the impact of infrastructure development on Nigeria's economic growth, and how can it be optimized?
5. How does Nigeria's global ranking in terms of HDI relate to its infrastructure development, and what implications does this have for policy and practice?
6. How can Nigeria's infrastructure be designed to be resilient and adaptable to climate change and natural disasters?

7. What opportunities and challenges exist in Nigeria's infrastructure development, and how can they be leveraged or addressed to promote sustainable development and economic growth?

Significant of the Study

The study on infrastructure development is a timely and conscious one as infrastructure development plays a critical role in economic growth and development of any nation thereby promoting quality of life of the citizens. Thus the study significant cannot be overstated as policy makers will find it beneficial in implementing policies that will promote economic growth and development. Also future researchers and students will find the study beneficial as the study stand as a reference point to them.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

Scope of the Study

The study will focus on the challenges and opportunities in Nigeria's infrastructure development, with a particular emphasis on the role of civil engineers and the impact of infrastructure development on economic growth and sustainable development. The study covers various types of engineering infrastructure, including transportation, energy and power, water and sanitation, and urban infrastructure.

Limitations of the Study

The study has several limitations, including:

1. **Geographical Scope:** The study is limited to Nigeria, and the findings may not be generalizable to other countries.
2. **Sectoral Focus:** The study focuses on the infrastructure development sector, and may not capture the complexities of other sectors that are also important for Nigeria's development.
3. **Methodological Limitations:** The study relied on secondary data sources, which have limitations in terms of accuracy and completeness.
4. **Timeframe:** The study is conducted within a specific timeframe, which limit the scope of the research and the ability to capture long-term trends and impacts.
5. **Stakeholder Perspectives:** The study does not capture the perspectives of all stakeholders, including policymakers, civil engineers, contractors, and communities affected by infrastructure development.
6. **Data Availability:** The study is limited by the availability of data on infrastructure development in Nigeria, which impacted the accuracy and reliability of the findings.

Despite these limitations, the study provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities in Nigeria's infrastructure development, and to contribute to the development of effective policies and strategies for promoting sustainable infrastructure development in the country.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

Construction

Construction refers to the process of creating, building, or assembling infrastructure, building of other structures, involving activities like designing, planning, and building with materials such as concrete, steel, and wood. This industry plays a critical role in shaping the built environment and support economic growth and development.

Infrastructure

Infrastructure refers to the fundamental systems and structures that support a country's economy, society and daily life, including transportation infrastructure, energy infrastructure, water sanitation infrastructure, and communication infrastructure.

Infrastructure Development

Infrastructure development refers to the process of planning, designing, construction, and maintaining infrastructure projects aiming to support economic growth, improve quality of life, enhance public safety, and promote sustainable development.

Current State and Types of Engineering Infrastructure

Nigeria infrastructure stock is estimated at only 30% of GDP, falling short of the 70% international benchmark set by the World Bank. The country requires substantial investment in various types of engineering infrastructure.

Referring to adopted boundary conditions in this study, the list below is limited to capital assets that serve the function of conveyance or channeling of people, vehicles, fluids, energy or information. They take the form either of a network or of a critical node used by vehicles, or used for the transmission of electro-magnetic waves. Infrastructure systems include both the fixed assets and the control systems and software required to operate, manage and monitor the systems, as well as any accessory buildings, plants or vehicles that are an essential part of the system.

1. Water Management Infrastructure

From Choate & Walter (1983) this includes:

- i. Drinking water supply, including the system of pipes, pumps, valves, filtration and treatment equipment and meters, including buildings and structures to house the equipment used for the collection, treatment and distribution of drinking water.
- ii. Sewage collection and disposal.
- iii. Drainage systems (storms sewers, ditches, etc).
- iv. Major irrigation systems (reservoirs, irrigation canals).
- v. Major flood control systems (dikes, levees, major pumping stations and floodgates)

2. Water Management Facilities

According to Choate & Walter (1983) these facilities includes:

- i. Solid waste landfills.
- ii. Solid waste incinerators.
- iii. Hazardous waste disposal facilities

3. Transportation Infrastructure

Grubler (1990) lists the following

- i. Road and highway networks, including structures (bridges, tunnels, culverts, retaining walls) signage and markings, electrical systems (street lighting and traffic lights) and edge treatments (curbs, sidewalks, and landscaping).
- ii. Railways, including structures, terminal facilities (rail yards, train stations) level crossings, signaling and communications systems.
- iii. Canals and navigable waterways requiring continuous maintenance (dredging, etc.).
- iv. Seaports and light houses
- v. Airports, including air navigational systems
- v. Mass transit systems (commuter rail systems, subways, tramways, trolleys and bus terminals).
- vi. Bicycle paths and pedestrian walkways.

4. Communication Infrastructures

From OECD (nd), the following are included

- i. Telephone networks (land lines) including switching systems.
- ii. Mobile phone networks.
- iii. Cable television networks including receiving stations and cable distribution networks
- iv. Internet backbone, including high-speed data cables, routers and servers as well as the protocols and other basic software required for the system to function.
- v. Communication satellites.
- vi. Undersea cables.
- vii. Major private, government or dedicated telecommunication networks, such as those used for internal communication and monitoring by major infrastructure companies, by governments, by the military or by emergency services.
- viii. Pneumatic tub mail distribution networks.

5. Energy Infrastructure

OECD (nd), lists the following:

- i. Electrical power network, including generation plants, electric grid, substations and local distribution.
- ii. Natural gas pipelines, storage and distribution terminals, as well as the local distribution network.
- iii. Petroleum pipelines, including associated storage and distribution terminals.
- iv. Steam or hot water production and distribution networks for district heating systems

6. Geophysical Monitoring Networks

From OECD (nd), the following are in this group:

- i. Meteorological monitoring networks.
- ii. Tidal and fluviometric monitoring networks.
- iii. Seismometer networks.
- iv. Remote sensing satellites

7. Other Systems or Networks

From OECD (nd), this includes:

Global positioning systems

It is important to note that certain systems or facilities that are similar to infrastructure are not included in the above list since.

- i. They are essentially services performed by people (commuter bus services, garbage collection services, emergency services).
- ii. They are facilities that are not necessarily part of or in the form of a network. Examples are parks, sports facilities.
- iii. They are essentially private-owned industrial plants that do not necessarily depend on a fixed distribution network like oil refineries. However, solid waste disposal facilities were included because they are often the critical nodal points of a network-like public service, e.g. garbage collection, and are usually publicly owned or heavily regulated.
- iv. Telecommunication systems are included to the extent that their function is limited to the conveyance of information like telephone system, but not when their function includes supplying the content of that information as in television or radio networks.

Sustainable Development in Nigeria's Infrastructure Development

The most commonly used definition of the term sustainable development is taken from the 1987 report titled 'Our common Future', by the World Commission on Environment and Development (known as the Brundland Commission).

By that formulation, Sustainable Development is "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs." Eldon and Bradley (2002). Since the report, the phrase had been broadened and modified while the term "sustainable" has gained usage because of increasing concern over exploitation of natural resources and economic development at the expenses of environmental quality. The popularity of the term stems from the dual objectives of environmental protection and economic growth. A former chairman of the United Nations Commission on Sustainable Development. Tan Sri Razali (n.d) in Eldon and Bradley (2002) pointed out thus: "the transfer of modern, environmentally sound technology to developing nations is the key global action to sustainable development."

Economic development must be sustainable which means that it should "keep going". The World Development Report 1999-2000 emphasizes the creation of sustainable improvements in the quality of life for all people as the principal goal of development policy. According to it, sustainable development has many objectives.

Besides increasing economic growth and meeting basic needs, the aim of lifting living standards includes a number of more specific goals such as:

- i. Improving peoples' health and educational opportunities.
- ii. Giving everyone the chance to participate in public life.

- iii. Helping to ensure a clean environment.
- iv. Promoting intergenerational equity

Thus, meeting the needs of the people in the present generation is essential in order to sustain the needs of future generations.

The Role Civil Engineer and Infrastructural Development

If the Civil Engineer is tagged “the designer and builder of the quality of life” ASCE (nd), then enormous responsibility is placed upon him in doing his job. His role of infrastructural development and maintenance in any nation cannot be toyed with. The Civil Engineer is therefore the fulcrum on which the sustainable infrastructural development of any nation revolves.

Most infrastructures are designed by Civil Engineers, except for telecommunications, electricity and monitoring networks that are designed mainly by electrical engineers. In the case of urban infrastructure, the general layout of roads, sidewalks, and public places may sometimes be designed by urbanists or architects, although the detailed design will still be performed by Civil Engineers.

The design and construction management process usually follow a sequential order of: preliminary studies, detailed survey, detailed engineering, authorization, tendering and construction supervision. In preliminary studies, existing and future traffic loads; information from existing air photos, maps, plans, satellite imageries; environmental impact assessments are conducted to ascertain impacts and conflicts with existing structures before proposing and costing various preliminary designs for recommendations. The detailed survey of the construction site is necessary to obtain as built drawings of existing infrastructure, exploratory pits and sample/test the soil(s) to determine nature, degree and extent of soil contamination. In detailed engineering plans, technical specifications, detailed bills of materials, detailed cost estimate and general works schedule are established.

Authorization involves: obtaining permits from environmental and regulatory agencies; owners and operators of assets affected by the work; and emergency services for preparation of contingency plans in case of emergencies. Tendering involves: preparation of administrative clauses and tender documents; organizing and announcing a call for tenders; answering contractors’ questions and matters arising during tendering process; receiving and analyzing tenders so as to make recommendation to the owner. Construction supervision includes: issuing order for commencement of works; scheduling meetings and obtaining information for all stakeholders; obtaining detailed work schedule and subcontractor list from the general contractor; obtaining detailed traffic diversion and emergency plans from the general contractor, obtaining proof of certification, insurance and bonds; examining shop drawings; following works in progress and reviewing changes, issuing certificates and making payments; and preparing “As Built” drawings.

ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

“Poverty anywhere is a threat to prosperity everywhere” ILO (1944).

Economic development can be defined as:

- i. The raising of income levels. To raise the income level of a developing country like Nigeria, there has to be the development of unused resources.
- ii. A discontinuous and spontaneous change in the stationary state which forever alters and displaces the equilibrium state previously existing.
- iii. More output and changes in the technical and institutional arrangement by which it is produced and distributed.
- iv. Changes in the composition of output and in the allocation of inputs by sectors.
- v. An innovative process leading to the structural transformation of social system.
- vi. Qualitative changes in economic wants, goods, incentives, institutions, productivity and knowledge, i.e. the upward movement of the entire social system.
- vii. A description of the underlying determinants of growth such as technological and structural changes.

Measurement of Economic Development

According to (Jhingan 2005), there are four major ways of measuring national development:

- i. GNP (Gross National Product) or GDP (Gross Domestic Product) - Is the total value of all the goods and services produced by a country in one year.

This includes the total income from foreign countries.

- ii. GNP per capita – This measure relates to an increase in the per capita real income of the economy over a period. An increase in per capita real income or output signifies a growing economy. The GDP per capita (Purchasing Power Parity, PPP) for Nigeria as at 2023 is \$6, 207.4. Libya is \$13, 848.8, Ghana is \$7,543.0, Germany is \$69. 027, China is \$24,569.3 and United States - \$82,769.4 all within the same period. Nigeria is therefore a lower middle-income country; World Bank Group (2025).

- iii. Welfare – economic development can also be measured in terms of economic welfare of individuals. When there is an increase in the consumption of goods and services by individuals, it is equally regarded as economic development. A sustained, secular improvement in material well-being most likely translates into increasing flow of goods and services.

- iv. Social indicators – these are often referred to as the basic needs for development. Basic needs focus on alleviation of poverty by providing basic human needs to the poor. The direct provision of such basic needs as health, education, food, water, sanitation and housing affects poverty in a shorter period and with fewer monetary resources than GNP/GNP per capita strategy which aims at increasing productivity and incomes of the poor automatically over the long run. Basic needs leads to a higher level of productivity and income through human development in the form of educated and healthy people.

Social indicators tell how different countries prefer to allocate the GNP among alternative uses. Some may prefer to spend more on education and less on hospitals. They give an idea about the presence, absence or deficiency of certain basic needs.

Table 1 below considers six social indicators for basic needs:

Table 1 Indicators of Development

S/N	Basic Needs	Indicator
1	Health	Life expectancy at birth
2	Education	Literacy signifying primary school enrolment as percent of population
3	Food	Caloric supply per head
4	Water supply	Infant mortality and percentage of population with access to potable water
5	Sanitation	Infant mortality and percentage of population with access to sanitation
6	Housing	None

Source: Jhingan, 2005

Basic Needs Vs Economic growth

There is strong correlation between basic needs and economic growth. Basic needs are concerned with ends while economic growth is a means to these ends. Countries that spend a large percentage of their GDP for public health are more efficient because they are able to reduce their infant mortality rate. (Jhingan, 2005).

The annual budgets in Nigeria and sectoral allocations are meant to address the needs of society. The national development plan of this country is the bedrock upon which the annual budgets are drawn.

From 2007 to 2009, the Federal Government of Nigeria ran a seven-point agenda in:

- i. Power and Energy.
- ii. Food security and agriculture.
- iii. Wealth creation and employment.
- iv. Transport.
- v. Land reforms.
- vi. Security and.
- vii. Education

These were identified areas of needs targeted for implementation so as to boost economic growth.

Nigeria's Development Agenda (1960 - Date)

Several rolling plans and initiatives have shaped Nigeria's development agenda. Some key ones are:

1. **Vision 20:2020** - aimed to turn Nigeria into one of the top 20 economies of the world by 2020 with the objectives of rapid economic growth to yield equitable social development and governance improvement; Common wealth gov. (2024).
2. **Seven - Point Agenda** - this agenda introduced in 2007 focused on infrastructure development, energy, transportation, agriculture, education, healthcare and security; kefas (2025).
3. **National Development plans (NDPs)** - Nigeria has had a good number of national development plans aimed at promoting economic growth, social development and infrastructure development; Naija quest (2023). some of the NDPs are:
First National Development Plan - 1962-1968
Second National Development Plan - 1970-1974
Third National Development Plan - 1975-1980: considered the most ambitious plan with a total capital expenditure of about 30 billion Naira and later revised to 43.3 billion Naira. Out of the projected expenditure governments only spent 29.3 billion Naira; Naija quest (2023). Key objectives of this plan included Rural Development, Agriculture Development and Economic growth.
4. **Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP)** - this plan was launched in 2017 and targeted the following:
 - ✓ restoration of economic growth,
 - ✓ promotion of economic diversification, and
 - ✓ -improvement of business environment Kefas (2025)
5. **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**
Nigeria is signatory to achievement of the SDGs whose billion lines are focused on a tripod of economic sustainability, social sustainability and environmental sustainability.
 - Economic sustainability involves raising access to resources and opportunities, increasing economic growth and reduction of poverty.
 - Social sustainability involves the promotion of social justice, equality and human rights while ensuring healthcare, education and cultural diversity for all.
 - Environmental sustainability refers to reduction of pollution, protection of natural resources and mitigation of climate change in order to preserve the earth's biodiversity and ecosystems.

The five pillars of Sustainable Development are: People, Peace, Prosperity, Partnership and Planet. "The SDGs put together are "a Universal call to action to end poverty, safeguard the planet and ensure all people enjoy peace and prosperity by the year 2030" – UNDP (2021). To achieve Sustainable Development globally, the United Nations adopted 17 Sustainable Development Goals in 2015 with the aim of addressing aspects of sustainable development such as education, health, poverty, inequality,

The sustainable Development Goals are shown in Figure 1 below

Figure 1 Source://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustainable_Development_Goals_and_Nigeria

Human Development Index (HDI)

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a comparative measure of life expectancy, literacy, education and standards of living for countries worldwide. It is a standard means of measuring well-being, especially child welfare. It is used to distinguish whether the country is a developed, a developing or an under-developed country, and also to measure the impact of economic policies on quality of life. The index was developed in 1990 by Pakistani economist Mahbub UI Haq and Indian economist Amartya Sen. Countries fall into three broad categories based on their HDI: high, medium and low human development.

The HDI is a composite index of achievements in three fundamental dimensions: living a long and healthy life, being educated and having decent standard of living. According to (Jhingan, 2005), the HDI value of a country is calculated by taking three indicators:

- i. Longevity, as measured by life expectancy at birth.
- ii. Educational attainment, as measured by a combination of adult literacy (two-thirds weight) and combined primary, secondary and tertiary enrolment ratio (one-third weight).
- iii. Decent standard of living, as measured by real GDP per capita based on purchasing power parity in terms of dollars (PPP \$).

To calculate HDI, an index is first calculated for each of the above listed indices (i.e., life expectancy index, education index and GDP index). For each indicator, minimum and maximum values are first chosen. See table 3 below

Table 2: Goalposts for calculating HDI

Indicator	Max. Value	Min. Value
Life Expectancy at birth (yrs)	85	25
Adult Literacy Rate (%)	100	0
Combined Gross Enrolment Ratio (%)	00	0
GDP per capita (PPP US \$)	40,000	100

Source: Jhingan, 2005

Performance in each indicator (dimension) is thus expressed as a value between 0 and 1 by applying the formula:

$$\text{Dimension index} = \frac{\text{Actual value} - \text{Minimum Value}}{\text{Maximum Value} - \text{Minimum Value}}$$

HDI is calculated as a simple average of the three-dimension indices. For each country therefore, the HDI value is indicative of the distance it has travelled towards the maximum possible value of 1 and how far it has to go to attain certain defined goals, e.g., an average life span of 85 years, access to education for all and a decent standard of living. The HDI ranks countries in relation to each other.

Countries with an HDI value below 0.5 are considered to have a low level of human development. Those with HDI of 0.5 to 0.8 have a medium level while those with 0.8 and above have a high level. The UNDP's Human Development Report, 2024 presented the HDI values, and HDI rank, for the year 2022 relating to 193 countries.

2024 RANKING OF COUNTRIES FOR HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX (HDI)

HDI is the most popular / widely used indicator for Human Development; Table 4 below indicates the ranking of countries by their HDI scores in 2024. Switzerland has the highest HDI with 0.967 as rating. Nigeria placed 161 out of 193 countries of 0.548; UNDP (2024), World Population Review (2024).

The Index considers Longevity, Purchasing Power and Education to provide a measure of Human Development.

Figure 2: HDI Ranking of Countries for 2024

Rank	Δ	Country or territory	HDI value	% annual growth (2010–2022)
1	—	Switzerland	0.967	▲ 0.24%
2	▼ (1)	Norway	0.966	▲ 0.25%
3	—	Iceland	0.959	▲ 0.28%
4	▲ (2)	Hong Kong	0.956	▲ 0.38%
5	▲ (1)	Denmark	0.952	▲ 0.35%
	—	Sweden		▲ 0.38%
7	▲ (8)	Ireland	0.950	▲ 0.38%
	▼ (3)	Germany		▲ 0.19%
9	▼ (1)	Singapore	0.949	▲ 0.25%
10	▲ (1)	Netherlands	0.946	▲ 0.26%
	▼ (1)	Australia		▲ 0.20%
158	▼ (1)	Haiti	0.552	▲ 1.74%
159	▲ (2)	Uganda	0.550	▲ 0.80%
	▼ (1)	Zimbabwe		▲ 1.12%
161	▲ (5)	Rwanda	0.548	▲ 1.02%
	▲ (2)	Nigeria		▲ 0.97%
163	▲ (2)	Togo	0.547	▲ 1.29%
164	▼ (3)	Pakistan	0.540	▲ 0.71%
	▼ (4)	Mauritania		▲ 0.51%
166	▲ (4)	Ivory Coast	0.534	▲ 1.07%
167	▲ (2)	Tanzania	0.532	▲ 0.64%
188	—	Mali	0.410	▲ 0.08%
189	▲ (2)	Niger	0.394	▲ 1.34%
	—	Chad		▲ 0.66%
191	—	Central African Republic	0.387	▲ 0.67%
192	▼ (2)	South Sudan	0.381	▼ 0.53%
193	NA ^[b]	Somalia	0.380	NA ^[c]

2024 GLOBAL RANKINGS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The ranking of countries is based on the total progress towards attaining the 17 SDGs. Countries are scored based on a total percentage of 100. Out of 193 countries, Nigeria placed 146th with an overall score of 54.58.

Figure 3 below shows the overall ranking of countries.

GLOBAL VULNERABILITY RANKINGS (ND - GAIN INDEX)

FIGURE 4: Vulnerability

<i>Rank</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Income group</i>	<i>Score</i>
1	Switzerland	Upper	0.251
2	Czech Republic	Upper	0.263
3	Norway	Upper	0.270
4	Canada	Upper	0.281
5	United Kingdom	Upper	0.285
6	Spain	Upper	0.292
6	Israel	Upper	0.292
8	Finland	Upper	0.295
9	United States	Upper	0.298
10	Austria	Upper	0.299
10	Germany	Upper	0.299
117	Viet Nam	Lower middle	0.458
119	Dem. People's Rep. of Korea	NA	0.459
120	Dominica	Lower middle	0.460
120	Namibia	Lower middle	0.460
122	Nicaragua	Lower middle	0.461
123	Belize	Lower middle	0.462
123	Nigeria	Low	0.462
125	Ecuador	Lower middle	0.465
126	Sri Lanka	Lower middle	0.466
127	Antigua and Barbuda	Upper middle	0.468
174	Afghanistan	Low	0.586
175	Marshall Islands	Lower middle	0.587
175	Mauritania	Lower middle	0.587
177	Sierra Leone	Low	0.598
178	Mali	Low	0.599
179	Sudan	Low	0.601
180	Eritrea	Low	0.602
181	Tonga	Lower middle	0.605
182	Somalia	Low	0.606
183	Guinea-Bissau	Low	0.617
184	Micronesia	Low	0.621
185	Niger	Low	0.632
186	Solomon Islands	Low	0.634
187	Chad	Low	0.646

OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES ARISING FROM INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT

The growing population of Nigeria with its economy keeps creating a huge demand for the development of infrastructure such as bridges, roads, housing, electricity, public transportation, etc. Numerous opportunities are therefore created for job creation, economic growth and investment.

OPPORTUNITIES

At the heart of the World Bank Groups' "Maximising Finance for Development" approach is the construction of modern, reliable and sustainable infrastructure; World Bank (2019). Investment in infrastructure offers new economic opportunities, facilitates investment in human capital and raises economic growth rates; World Bank (2018). Specifically in developing economies and emerging markets, including Nigeria, achieving poverty reduction and shared prosperity, economic growth and development, tackling climate change and attaining the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) require massive increase in infrastructure investment; Oyedele (2019).

Further opportunities available due to construction and infrastructure development in Nigeria are as follows:

1. **Infrastructure Development Finance** – many infrastructure funds targeted at driving economic growth and development now exist in Nigeria.

Some of them are:

- ✓ Presidential Infrastructure Development Fund (PIDF) – this is managed by Nigeria Sovereign Investment Authority (NSIA) and established to facilitate the execution of critical infrastructure projects.
 - ✓ Nigeria Infrastructure Debt Fund (NIDF) – this was established as a closeended investment trust to equip investors with stable and regular income via debt investments in infrastructure projects.
 - ✓ Nigeria Infrastructure Fund – this fund is also managed by NSIA and targets high-priority projects with potency of economic growth stimulation.
 - ✓ Chapel Hill Denham Nigeria Infrastructure Debt Fund – this 200 billion Naira issuance program was established for investment in infrastructure projects.
 - ✓ Infrastructure Bank Plc – this specialized bank was established in 2010 with focus areas on infrastructure sectors like energy, water, telecommunications and transportation. It supports Nigeria's infrastructure development by providing project finance, corporate loans and advisory services.
2. **Public Private Partnerships (PPPs)** – in order to bridge infrastructure deficit in Nigeria and drive economic growth, PPPs have been promoted.

It has yielded the following benefits

- ✓ **Job creation** – employment opportunities are generated during feasibility, construction and operation phases
- ✓ **Reduced financial burden** – financial risks are shared between the public and private sectors
- ✓ **Improved infrastructure** – high quality infrastructure are assured since the private sector often operate the infrastructure before transferring it to government or final beneficiary.
- ✓ **Increased efficiency** – the private sector participation brings in expertise and efficiency into the infrastructure development.

Example of PPP projects in Nigeria

- ✓ Lekki Deep Sea port – this is a project between Lagos State Government and a Private Consortium – China Harbor Engineering Company and Tolaram Group, operating through Lekki Port LFTZ Enterprise Limited. A 45year concession agreement under the Build, Own, Operate and Transfer (BOOT) Model of PPP was adopted for this project.

- ✓ Abuja – Kaduna Railway – the Federal government and a Chinese Consortium - China Civil Engineering Construction Corporation (CCECC) partnered on this project. The construction of the 186.5km standard gauge railway which was delivered in December 2014 though commercial operations commenced in July 2016 was executed by CCECC; Aiddata (2021).
 - ✓ Lagos – Ibadan Expressway – despite being doubtful in respect of its success, a 25 year concession agreement was struck between the Federal Government and Bi-Courtney Highway Services. The company was to expend N89.53 billion in upgrading the road and to recoup the investment through tolls and charges; Business Day (2009).
3. **Urbanization and City Development** – modern cities with adequate infrastructure are greatly needed to match Nigeria ‘s rapid urbanization. Some notable Nigerian cities have faced challenges of housing shortages, inadequate infrastructure and environmental degradation in the past 20years due to population growth, rural-urban migration and economic development. Examples of such cities are: Abuja, PortHarcourt, Kano, Lagos, Ibadan, etc. Open Edition Books (2025). Notwithstanding, the urbanization challenges provide great opportunities for innovation, cultural exchange and economic growth.

Table 3 below Population growth of some Nigerian Cities from 1952-2000 AD, (in millions)

City	1952*	1963*	1972**	1982**	% Increase in 30 years**	2000**
Lagos	.27	.66	1.57	4.10	1,418	6.90
Ibadan	.46	.63	1.48	2.84	518	4.70
Ogbomoso	.14	.32	.50	.81	479	1.50
Kano	.13	.30	.58	1.50	1,054	2.60
Ile-Ife	.11	.13	.20	.32	199	.43
Abeokuta	.08	.19	.29	.62	641	1.32
Onitsha	.08	.17	.25	.31	309	.73
Oyo	.07	.11	.17	.28	293	.45
Port Harcourt	.07	.18	.35	.91	1,183	2.11
Enugu	.06	.17	.33	.85	1,244	1.75
Aba	.06	.13	.20	.33	471	.56
Maiduguri	.06	.14	.27	.71	1,147	1.48
Zaria	.05	.16	.26	.42	678	.68
Benin City	.05	.10	.20	.51	846	1.30
Katsina	.06	.09	.14	.23	263	.42
Sokoto	.05	.09	.18	.46	775	.98
Calabar	.05	.08	.15	.39	816	.61
Kaduna	.04	.15	.35	.92	1,935	2.14
Ilorin	.04	.21	.41	1.10	2,480	2.12
Jos	.04	.09	.18	.46	1,076	.84
Minna	.02	.03	.09	.20	900	.41

Source: Open Edition Books (2025)

Table 4 below Shows the Percentage of people Residing in Urban Areas in the world, Africa and Nigeria (1950 - 2025)

Year	World	Africa	Nigeria
1950	29.2	14.5	10.1
1955	31.2	16.3	12.1
1960	34.2	18.3	14.4
1965	35.5	20.6	17.0
1970	36.6	22.9	20.0
1975	37.8	25.2	23.4
1980	39.5	27.8	27.1
1985	42.2	30.6	31.0
1990	45.2	33.9	35.2
1995	48.1	37.3	39.3
2000	51.1	40.7	43.3
2005	53.9	44.0	47.2
2010	59.3	50.7	54.8
2020	62.0	53.9	58.3
2025	64.6	57.1	61.6

Source: Open Edition Books (2025)

4. **Housing and Urban Development**

The current housing deficit in Nigeria is 28 million units, while approximately N21trillion is required to close the gap; FGN (2023); Estate Intel (2024); Buyletlive (2024). Lack of affordable housing options, rapid population growth and urbanization are responsible for these challenges. Notwithstanding, it offers opportunities in investment for affordable housing.

Secondly, urban renewal initiatives such as upgrade of slums, public space development and road construction are investment opportunities required in many Nigerian cities.

5. **Digital Infrastructure**

The Nigerian telecommunications market size was estimated at USD 9.09 billion in 2024 and projected to reach USD 11.43 billion by 2029; Itive (2025).

Furthermore, the key areas of investment are:

- ✓ 4G and 5G Network Expansion
- ✓ Fibre Optic Infrastructure
- ✓ Broadband Development
- ✓ Rural Connectivity
- ✓ Green Telecom Infrastructure to reduce carbon footprint.

6. **Energy and Power**

Renewable energy sources such as solar, hydro and wind offer great opportunities for investment in power generation and distribution especially considering the abundant potential in Nigeria. According to World Bank Group (2023) renewable energy accounted for only 0.8% in 2022. With the country's target of uplifting this share of renewable energy to 30% in 2030 and 96% by 2050 (Enerdata, 2024), this is a huge opportunity for investors. If our energy supply must toe the line of sustainability, dependence on fossil fuel must be reduced while the vast renewable energy potential must be unlocked; Mordor Intelligence (2025).

Secondly, power losses can be reduced by upgrading Nigeria's Transmission and Distribution Infrastructure thereby improving electricity supply. This also is an opportunity for investors.

7. **Water and Sanitation**

Water supply infrastructure such as pipelines, distribution networks and treatment plants are areas where Nigeria needs tangible investments. What is the percentage of functional Water Boards in Nigeria today? The pipes are mostly underground gathering rust where they have not been vandalized. Dr. Ezeji Joachim, a water and ecosystem specialist opined that none of the 36 state government have effectively managed water board; EWASH (2023). The private sector can easily and profitably manage this. This is a huge investment opportunity in all cities, towns and villages all over the country.

Sanitation and Waste Management offers opportunities in waste management facilities, circular economy of turning waste to wealth ie recycling infrastructure and modern sanitation systems.

8. **Transportation**

The three most prominent areas of investment here are Railway Development, Airport Development and Port Development.

a. Railway Development – just like the revamped Abuja – Kaduna Rail line, standard gauges are required in many other routes. Ready investors can opt for Ajaokuta – Abuja; Enugu – Aba- Onitsha rail lines and others which would easily have a lot of passengers. Thus, opportunities for investment in rolling stock, rail infrastructure and services abound.

Though significant progress have been achieved recently in Nigerian railway development, the country currently has railway network of 3,505km of the narrow gauge (Colonial gauge) and 669km of standard gauge (modern gauge) Chukwurah, Okeke, Isimah and Igwe (2022).

Since all the colonial gauges are to be changed to modern gauges, a lot of investment opportunities 81% exist therein for investors. Added to this are the new routes that would obviously contribute to boosting railway transportation in Nigeria.

Table 5 below shows the railway construction in Nigeria.

Table 5 Railway Construction in Nigeria

Section	Year	Distance	Gauge
Lagos – Ibadan	1898-1901	193km	Narrow Gauge
Ibadan – Jebba	1901-1909	295km	‘
Kano – Baro	1907-1911	562km	‘
Jebba – Minna	1909 -1916	225km	‘
Enugu – Makurdi	1914-1916	243km	‘
Kaduna Junction – Kafanchan	1916-1924	179km	‘
Kafanchan – Jos	1924-1927	101km	‘
Kuru – Bauchi	1958-1961	1661m	‘
Bauchi – Gombe	1961-1963	155km	‘
Gombe – Maiduguri	1963-1964	302km	‘
Itakpe - Ajaokuta	1986-2020	277km	Standard Guage on going
Ajaokuta – Warri	1986-2020	275km	Standard Guage
Port-Harcourt – Onne	On going	19km	1067mm

Source: Chukwurah, Okeke, Isimah and Igwe (2022).

- Ongoing Railway Projects

The proposed coastal railway project linking Lagos with Calabar is to be financed with a Chinese loan worth \$12 billion while the Lagos - Kano modernization is equally in progress; Proshare (2018).

- Completed Railway Projects

Within the Lagos - Kano modernization project, the Kaduna - Abuja segment has been completed; Proshare (2018).

b. Airport Development – opportunities abound for investment in aviation services, logistics and airport infrastructure.

The Lekki – Epe International Airport is a new airport in progress of development at Lagos with a passenger per annum planned capacity of 5 million; CAPA (2025). By January, 2025 the Lagos State Government, under a PPP arrangement signed an Mou with Summa Group to develop and construct the International Airport.

Federal Airports Authority of Nigeria (FAAN) is also modernizing and upgrading several Nigerian Airport infrastructures so as to enhance overall travel experience and increase passenger capacity.

c. Port Development – investment opportunities exist in Nigeria’s ports as they are being expanded and modernized in the areas of infrastructure, logistics and services. Nigeria has the following ports:

- ✓ Lagos port complex (Tin Can Island and Apapa ports)
- ✓ Calabar port
- ✓ Port Harcourt port
- ✓ Onne port
- ✓ Warri port
- ✓ Delta port, also called Escraves port

Other oil and gas terminals, private jetties and terminals exist along the country’s coastline. All port operations are under the management and regulation of the Nigerian Ports Authority.

CHALLENGES

Some challenges associated with the construction and infrastructure development in Nigeria are:

a. Inadequate Funding

This challenge affects infrastructure construction and development in Nigeria in the following ways:

- Insufficient government allocation
- Dependence on foreign aids
- Limited private sector investment

- Corruption and mismanagement of funds allocated

The effects of inadequate funding include:

- ✓ Poor quality infrastructure
- ✓ Increased costs due to delays
- ✓ Hindrances to economic growth, reduced competitiveness, increase in transportation and logistics.
- ✓ Project delays and abandonment - the Manbilla Hydro Power Project first conceived in 1972 and approved in 2007 by the Federal Executive Council is a case study in economic losses of delayed projects. With a capacity of 3050 MN and cost of 5.8 million (85% funded by China's Export - Import Bank and outstanding 15% by Nigerian Federal Government), the completion Date is 2030; Wikipedia (2025). Upon completion, this would be the largest installation for power in Nigeria and one of Africa's largest hydroelectric power stations.

b. Bureaucratic Red tapes

Very often delays in project approvals and execution are a result of regulating hurdles and complex administrative progress. Features of bureaucratic red tapes include:

- Inefficient institutional framework
- inadequate capacity and weak institutions are antithesis to progress especially in decision making.
- Corruption - approval processes are unnecessarily delayed because of bribery and corruption.
- Complex regulatory frameworks - delays and confusions are occasioned by multiple agencies of government.
- Lack of transparency and accountability - requirements and procedures that are unclear bred confusion and corruption. Every agency is a lord unto itself and weak or non-existent synchronisation yields very poor accountability.

Resulting from bureaucratic red tapes are:

- Loss of opportunities
- Investor frustration - what happened to the Ease of Driving Business? Or is it just a proclamation without action?
- Delayed Project Execution
- Economic Losses.

c. Decayed Infrastructure

Infrastructure decay in Nigeria affects many sectors - energy, transportation, housing, water, airports, telecommunications etc. The causes of the decay are not farfetched and they include:

- Lack of maintenance
- Corruption
- Over-reliance on imports
- Insufficient funding
- Poor planning

The effects of infrastructure decay include:

- ✓ Environmental degradation
- ✓ Increased cost of maintenance or replacement
- ✓ Reduced competitiveness
- ✓ Economic Losses - infrastructure decay leads to 2% loss in GDP annually - a significant loss }
Reduced quality of life - no wonder that Nigerian Human development Index is only 0.548
placing at 161 out of 193 countries; UNDP (2024); World Population review (2024) Nigeria's
Infrastructure Deficit is presently 1.8/5.0 and Grade Level; Ali (2025).

d. Security issues

Project risks and costs have increased with security challenges in many parts of the country. The federal Ministry of Works have included security costs on projects in the country. Apart from construction and

infrastructure development, oil and gas sectors have significant share of these security challenges. The security challenges included:

- i. Armed robbery and theft
- ii. Terrorism and insurgency
- iii. Community related issues
- iv. Kidnapping and abduction
- v. Vandalism and sabotage

Security challenges affect projects in the following ways:

- ✓ Increased costs
- ✓ Loss of lives and injuries
- ✓ Project delays and cancellations
- ✓ Damage to reputation

Security challenges are caused by:

- Lack of government support
- Poor community engagement
- Inadequate security measures
- Corruption and negligence.

e. Poor Leadership Commitment

Progress has greatly been hampered due to lack or inadequate commitment from leaders. Compromises and sabotage of leaders and the led cannot be ruled out. Poor leadership commitment hampers projects as follows:

- Inadequate resource allocation - poor resource management and insufficient funding are employed to kill or frustrate projects
- Ineffective project management - inadequate monitoring & evaluation and lack of accountability where leadership is ineffective
- Corruption and lack transparency - diversion of funds, nepotism, embezzlement, hiding of details are clear manifestation of corruption.
- Talent flight and brain drain - skilled individuals seek opportunities elsewhere due to low moral occasioned by poor leadership.
- Lack of clear vision and priorities - inconsistencies in policies epitomized by frequent changes and lack of clear vision can only catalyze poor funding.

Consequent upon poor leadership commitment, projects are:

- ✓ Abandoned or delayed
- ✓ Economic stagnation result from inadequate infrastructure
- ✓ Quality of life fops - where health, education, transportation and power facilities are not adequate, citizens' expenses and low quality of life.

HOW INFRASTRUCTURE IMPROVES QUALITY OF LIFE

Infrastructure development across the nation has significant effects on the citizenry. Some of these effects include:

1. Increased economic opportunities - infrastructure development create jobs, create and grow businesses, stimulate economies and encourage learning and innovation. The Nigerian Railway development and major projects have become a huge gold mine to Chinese companies.
2. Access to basic services - basic services such as education, portable water, healthcare, electricity, etc. are accessed when associated infrastructure are made available. The Mambilla Hydropower Project would provide electricity and contribute to the national grid.
3. Enhanced Public Safety - the provision of solar electricity on Nigeria roads and streets particularly from dusk till dawn reduces crimes greatly. Emergency healthcare and fire services also contribute to public safety.

4. Improved environmental quality - green telecom infrastructure reduces carbon footprint, electromagnetic radiation and noise pollution. Similarly, air pollution urban heat island effects are mitigated with green infrastructure such as green spaces and parks.
 5. Improved transportation - travel times are reduced while economic opportunities are increased with reliable transportation infrastructure. Movement of people, goods and services from rural to urban areas or from city to city are greatly enhanced. Citizens can go to work in states different from where they reside and return to their loved one's same day. Adoption of mass transit or public transportation system reduces carbon footprint while workers make savings on transportation. Cost of logistics also becomes lower leading to cheaper goods and services.
- Note that the flip side of the above benefits is low quality of life for citizens.

MAJOR INFRASTRUCTURE IMPACTING ON QUALITY OF LIFE IN NIGERIA

- 1) Energy Infrastructure - the withdrawal of fuel subsidy since May 29, 2023 is no doubt a bitter pill in the mouths of citizens. Populations of cars and vehicles on the roads have grossly reduced. Fuel, kerosine, diesel, and electricity tariffs have worsened the plight of the common man. With the increased minimum wage, the quality of life of the average Nigerian has drastically dropped.
- 2) Transportation Infrastructure - the subsidy withdrawal led to drastic increase in transportation and logistics costs.
- 3) Housing and Urban Infrastructure - the cost of housing averagely have attached 50% increase in most cities. Construction materials cost has more than doubled between May 29, 2023 and today.
- 4) Water and Sanitation Infrastructure - cost of water abstraction and treatment plus general maintenance of pipelines, treatment and sewage systems have grossly increased.
- 5) Digital Infrastructure - cost of internet connectivity, networks and data are obviously higher compared to pre-May 29, 2023.

COUNTRY RATINGS ON SUSTAINABLE INFRASTRUCTURE

Various frameworks such as Country Sustainability Ranking and Sustainable Development Report can help to assess countries regarding sustainable infrastructure availability. Hence, Table 2.5 is a good measure of sustainable infrastructural development for countries globally. Nigeria is ranked 146 with 54.58 percentage attainment.

FACTS ON NIGERIA'S INFRASTRUCTURE

1. There is a DFID five - year E 95m Nigeria Infrastructure Advisory Facility II (NIAF) programme which provides demand - led advice and assistance to Nigeria government bodies at federal and state levels so as to meet the national infrastructure challenge on power, infrastructure development finance, roads, effective cities and climate change sectors; Adam Smith International (2023).
2. Nigeria currently faces a 100 billion dollar annual investment gap in infrastructure; Vanguardngr (2019); \$ 150 billion gap annually over the next 30 years; Augusto & Co (2023).
3. Nigeria's physical infrastructure gap is estimated to reach \$3tn in 30 years ; Punchng (2022).
4. Nigeria ranked 115 out of 140 countries by global competitiveness while it placed 112 out of 135 countries in the 2017/2018 ranking ; Proshare (2018).

The 12 ranking pillars for assessment are:

1. Institutions
2. Health
3. ICT adoption
4. Macroeconomic environment
5. Infrastructure
6. Skills
7. Product market
8. Labour market

9. Financial system
10. Market size
11. Business Dynamism, and
12. Innovation capability

CONCLUSION

From 4 parameters of development Nigeria performed as follows:

	Rank	Score
Sustainable Development goals attainment	- 146 out of 193 countries;	54.58%
Human Development Index	- 161 out of 193 countries;	0.548
ND Gain Index (Vulnerability Ranking)	- 123 out of 187 countries;	0.462
Global Competitiveness	- 116 out of 140 countries;	48.33%

The government should therefore give priority to infrastructure development with focus in security, energy, transportation, agriculture, healthcare, housing and ICT. Government must be very deliberate in ensuring sustainability of any infrastructure development. Clear policy guidelines drawn from irrevocable national rolling plans are imperative to amid government deviations with leadership changes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are recommendations to improve Nigeria's Infrastructure rating

1. Infrastructure development must be addressed through timely repairs and regular maintenance.
2. Material and construction practices must be improved through use of quality construction materials, good workmanship backed by top quality designs.
3. Infrastructure functionality must be optimized through provision of preventive maintenance knowledge, ensuring proper maintenance of water sources and addressing technical issues.
4. Robust institutional frameworks for effective infrastructure planning, development and maintenance must be in place.
5. Transparency and thorough accountability of infrastructure planning development and maintenance would discourage mismanagement and corruption.
6. Community engagement and participation have to be encouraged for infrastructure planning, development and maintenance to promote sense of responsibility and ownership.
7. Efficient user free collection system that would help generate revenue for infrastructure upgrade and maintenance should be established.
8. Leveraging external funding options such as international organizations and private investors can provide funding opportunities for infrastructure development and maintenance.
9. Increase in funding and budget allocation to ensure adequacy of funding for infrastructural development abinitio.
10. Maintenance fund should be part of project costing abinitio retained with a maintenance bank/organization where the funds can never be used except for intended purpose should be part of the infrastructural development system. This maintenance bank/organization should operate independently without government interference.
11. Robust infrastructure policy derived from irrevocable national rolling plans is imperatives for sustainable development of Nigerian infrastructure without abandonment midway as has been the case previously.
12. Well - developed PPP framework under clear regulatory environment as in Egypt, Morocco, South Africa, and Kenya in that order of ranking should be established to accelerate sustainable infrastructure development.

REFERENCES

- Adam Smith International (2023) Tackling Nigeria’s Infrastructure challenges: A flexible facility supporting the power and transportation sectors, urban development and climate change resilience. Available from <https://adamsmithinternational.com/projects/tacklingNigeria-infrastructure-challenges/> Accessed: Feb 20, 2023.
- AidData (2021) Project ID:195 China Exim bank provides \$500 million preferential buyer’s credit for phase 1 (Abuja-Kaduna Section) of Nigerian Railway Modernization Project. Available from China.AidData.org. Accessed: March 21, 2025
- Ali, S.E. (2012) “Sustainable Engineering Infrastructure: The key to National Economic Development (A case study of Warri/Effurun, Delta State, Nigeria)” A project submitted in partial fulfillment of the Requirements for the award of Masters of Engineering (M.Eng) in Water Resources and Environmental Health Engineering in the Department of Civil Engineering, Family of Engineering, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria.
- Ali, S.E. (2025) “Advancing the Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria Irrespective of Climate Change - The Engineering Imperatives” A paper delivered in Commemoration of 2025 World Engineering Day on March 04, 2025 at Nigerian Society of Engineers Asaba, Delta State, Nigeria.
- ASCE (nd) Excerpt from The American Society of Civil Engineering Administration material. Audu, M.O and Adeize, O.M (2024) Overview of Nigeria’s Infrastructural Development. Available from <https://doi.org/10.7454/jid.v7.i3.1148> Accessed: March 20, 2025 Augusto & Co (2023) Structural Reform, the competitiveness Question and the currency command rum Available from augusto.com/publications Accessed: March 22, 2015.
- Business Day (2009) Concession of Lagos -Ibadan Expressway Available from businessday.ng Accessed: March 21, 2025.
- BuyLetLive (2024) Bridging the Housing Gap: Why Nigeria Desperately Needs More Affordable homes. Available from buyletlive.com Accessed: March 21, 2025
- CAPA (2025) Lekki - Epe International Airport Available from eforaviation.com Accessed: March 21, 2025
- CAPA (2025) Lekki - Epe International Airport; Available from eforaviation.com Accessed: March 22,2025
- Chaote , P. and Walter, S (1983) “America in Ruins: The Decaying Infrastructure”. Tx: Duke University Press. (Accessed: March 22, 2025).
- Chukwurah, G; Isimah, M.O. and Igwe, A. (2022) Assessment of the performance of Railway Transportation in Nigeria from 1970 to 2010. Available from researchgate.net Accessed: March 22, 2025
- Common Wealth Governance (2024) National Development Plan of Nigeria Available from commonwealthgovernance.org Accessed: March 22, 2025.
- Eldon, D.E and Bradley, F.S (2002) “Environmental Science: A study of Interrelationship”8th ed. Boston: McGraw Hill Publishers.
- Enerdata (2024) Nigeria Energy consumption (% of total final energy consumption) – Nigeria Available from data.worldbank.org Accessed: March 21, 2025.
- Estate Intel (2024) Nigeria’s 2024 Housing Allocation can only deliver 2,439 Housing Units Available from estateintel.com Accessed: March 21, 2025
- EWASH (2023) FG should take over management of state water boards Available from washnigeria.com Accessed: March 21, 2015.
- FGN (2023) Nigeria needs N21tr to address housing deficit Available from statehouse.gov.ng. Accessed: March 21, 2025
- Grubler, A (1990) “The Rise and Fall of Infrastructures: Dynamics of Evolution and Technological Change in Transport” (Online). Available from: <http://www.iiasa.ac.at/Admin/PUB/Documents/XB-90-704.pdf>. (Accessed: March 22, 2025).
- Hornby, A.S. (2000) “Oxford advance Learner’ Dictionary of Current English 6th ed. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press. Accessed March 22, 2025.
- ILO (1944) Working out of Poverty: Declaration Concerning the aims and Purpose of the International Labour Organization, Philadelphia (online). Available from

- http://www.ilo.org/globa/About_the_ILO/Mainpillars/Workingoutofpoverty/langen/index.htm (Accessed: March 22, 2025).
- Itive, S. (2025) “Future of Telecommunication Infrastructure – Trends & Insights” A paper presented at the Nigerian Society of Engineers Webinar services of march 19, 2025
- Jhingan, M.I. (2005) “The Economics of Development and Planning” 38th ed. Mayur Vihar. Deihi: Vrinda Publication Ltd.
- Kumar, D (2005) Infrastructure in India (online). Available from: <http://www.129.3.20.41/eps/urb/papers/0506/0506002.pdf> (Accessed: March 22, 2025).
- Kefas, J. (2025) Economic Planning of Nigeria from 1960 – Data Available from academia.edu/39 (Accessed: March 22, 2025)
- Modor Intelligence (2025) Nigeria Renewable Energy Market size & share Available – Growth trends & forecasts (2025-2030) Available from modorintelligence.com Accessed: March 21, 2025.
- Naija Quest (2023) Development planning in Nigeria - History, Stages, Problems Available from naijaquest.com/d. Accessed: March 22, 2025.
- OECD (nd). “Economic Infrastructure” (online) Available from: <http://www.oecd.org/dataoecd/12/25/43860714.pdf>. (Accessed: March 22, 2025).
- Open Edition Books (2025) urbanization and urban problems in Nigeria. Available from books.openedited.org Accessed: March 21, 2015
- Oyedele, O.A (2012) The challenges of Infrastructure development in democratic government. Construction Economics and Management 1, 6119 1/15 FIG Working Week 2012.
- Oyedele, O.A (2019) Infrastructure Investment in developing economies Available from scholar.google.com Accessed: March 22, 2025
- Proshare (2018) Ralling for Railways in Nigeria Available from Proshare.co/artic Accessed : March 22, 2025
- Punchng (2022) Nigeria’s infrastructure quality low, says World bank. Available from <https://punchng.com/nigerias-infrastructure-quality-low-says-world-bank> Accessed: Feb 20, 2023.
- Trading Economics (2020) Nigeria Competitiveness Index. Available from tradingeconomics.com. Accessed: March 22, 2025.
- Umar, K; Ogbu, C. and Ereke, E. (2019). The challenges of Infrastructural Development in Nigeria: An Assessment of The Pains and The Gains. Available from <http://www.academicresearchjournals.org/IJPSD/index.html>
- UNDP (2021): Government OF Nigeria launches Nigeria SGDS Implementation Plan 2020 – 2030 with support from UNDP.... Available @ undp.org/Nigeria. Accessed – Mar. 03, 2025.
- UNDP (2024): Huma Developmen Report... Available @ hdr.undp.org. Accessed - Mar. 03, 2025.
- UNDP (2024): 2022 Human Development Indexn (2024 report) ... Available @ en.m.wikipedia.org. Accessed – Mar. 03, 2025
- Vanguardngr (2019) Infrastructure gap: World Bank, IFC reaffirm support for Nigeria Available from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2019/09/infrastructure-gap-world-bank-ifcreaffim>..... Accessed Feb 20, 2023
- Wikipedia (2025) Mambilla Hydroelectric Power Station; Available from Wikipedia.org Accessed: March 22, 2025
- World Bank (2018) The world Bank Annual Report Available from: worldbank.org Accessed: March 22, 2025
- World Bank Group (2023) Renewable energy consumption (% of total final energy consumption) – Nigeria. Available from data.worldbank.org Accessed: March 21, 2025.
- World Bank Group (2025) GDP Per Capital, PPP (Current International \$) – Nigeria Available from data.worldbank.org Accessed: March 22, 2025.
- World Population Review (2024): Human Development Index (HDI) dy country 2024... Available @ <https://worldpopulationreview.com>